
Self-Directedness, Motivation and Students' Performance in Technology and Livelihood Education

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ABSTRACT: The study sought to determine the extent to which students perceive level of self-directedness, motivation, and their performances as a Grade 10 students. The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. This focused on describing the students' perceptions of the level of self-directedness in TLE in terms of being a dependent learner, interested learner, involved learner, and self-directed learner. The study's findings revealed that student respondents' perceptions of their level of self-directedness fall only on being a dependent learner which is the stage 1 on self-directed learner. They are merely dependent on extrinsic variables which most of the learner-respondents always perceive and consider themselves as a dependent learner. This reflected the result on their perceived level of motivation which findings shown that the learners corresponded a lot on extrinsic variables. The study revealed that self-directedness and student's performance have no significant relationship. However, there is a weak relationship between the learner's level of motivation and written performance variable. Further research must be conducted along this light, to explore the extent of self-directedness to have positive effect to the students' performance in TLE.

KEYWORDS: self-directedness motivation written task performance task

1. INTRODUCTION

Self-directedness is one process that can promote and establish lifelong learning among students. It is true that people learn new things every day. Whether in school or at home, learning ultimately comes down to being a choice. Some students who are enrolled in traditional school settings still partake in self-directed learning because they want to. Other people choose to learn in unconventional ways and strictly rely on self-directed learning. As defined Self-directed learning, or SDL, is an educational process that gives power to the student to choose how they want to learn. Students receive guidance from a teacher, whether that teacher be in a school setting or online. Teachers may also be tutors or parents who are homeschooling their kids. Once a student is given their educational goal or target, they have freedom to choose how they achieve it. With the emerging gap in the Philippine educational system brought about by the decline in the delivery of quality education for the past years mainly caused by the onslaught of the Covid-19 pandemic and other factors presented by the Department of Education, the researcher foresees self-directedness as one factor that can bridge the gap in the educational system. Teaching the students, the process of self-directedness as it applies to their performances and/ or skills of today's youth can be a major innovation that could probably produce lifelong learners. According to the article published by UNICEF under the title "Let me learn," a learning crisis campaign, it argues that nearly two-thirds of 10-year-olds are unable to read and understand that simple statement, and that without prompt response, this global learning crisis will become a generational catastrophe. Even before the pandemic, our educational systems were failing our children. COVID-19 has aggravated the learning crisis, with children in almost every country falling behind. On a press release done by the Department of Education the implementation of blended learning in 2021, Former DepEd Secretary Leonor Magtolis Briones emphasized that online learning is only one option from the menu of learning modalities. These modalities will be offered appropriately depending on the situation of the learners' households. "We have come out with a variety, with menu of options, online is not the only answer, there's a huge debate in the Philippines on how useful or whether it is really a good way of teaching learners, so we have online, we have televisions, we have radio. If all else fails, then learning modules are being printed so that these will be delivered in various pick-up points or either parents or for the village officials to distribute to the learners," she said. It is true that learning continued despite the pandemic, but the quality of learner produced were still questionable. Resiliency is one virtue that can be further inculcated within the learners for them to be able to cope with situation like this. The ability to learn in on their own and being motivated of the students is a must these days. This is the main reason why the researcher is eager to conduct a study about the mediating effect of motivation on self-directedness and student's performance in technology and livelihood education.

Every learner is a one-of-a-kind individual, distinctive in psychological and emotional turn of events, social development, capacity, inspiration, desire, potential, requirements, interests, and self-attributes, and learning styles. Aside from this, there are different

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elements on students' differences, and it compromises state of living, intelligent quotient, varieties in past learning encounters, metacognition, and maybe varieties in the degree of coinciding between the student and the educational plan or school curriculum. Considering these variables, cooking for singular contrasts is planned neither to limit the hole between learner's potential and their capacities and execution on a specific learning task. It should target understanding why learners are capable or unfit to learn well and discovering suitable approaches to assist them with learning.

These factors of differences also affect teachers on how they will teach students. Most of the educators, parents and other stakeholders are not aware of the significance of knowing the different learning styles to create programs or activities that will increase the students' skill performance engaging them to be self-motivated learners.

Mustafa N. (2020) discussed in his paper how learners negatively affect by the coronavirus 2019-2020 pandemic in terms of distance learning, unequal access to technology, and unequal access to educational resources. Aside from different learning styles, these people also help most of the learners' learning process. As we speak today, learners struggle on doing their tasks without anyone around them but themselves. Zhao (2010) found out in his study that on doing their paper, learners listen more to teachers' feedback rather than to peers even they do not know its significance. Student interviews uncovered learners' passive acceptance of teacher feedback and the facilitative role of first language use in peer interaction. As the teacher and researcher teach her student in TLE via self-learning modules, it is noticeable that learners find hard time answering it even doing assigned performance tasks ask them to do especially they have no one to ask about what and how they are going to do the said activity. It also seems that learners gain confidence from their peers when they have common output and when the facilitator guides them and translates or rephrases the instruction for them. On this modular setup, those who have access to the internet can ask questions about the activity but to those who unfortunately cannot provide or connect to the internet, they skip it and leave it blank. As the researcher and teacher observes on her class, they only get motivated on the subject if the topic is somewhat related to them or if they are exposed to the materials they are going to use on activity and when their parents push them to do it with their guidance. According to Abd-El-Fattah, S. M. (2010) giving chances for control and choice all along can considerably improve the entering motivational state, which then affects whether learners will be accountable to be self-directed and continue in their learning tasks.

The teacher and researcher, have the conviction that learners ought to learn what is intended for them to learn and they should be the key role player in it. Students acknowledged how active teaching and engagement positively impacted their learning (Lumpkin A. et., al., 2015). To address the necessities of the learners, teachers ought to give them an assortment of learning opportunities for compelling learning, for example, utilizing enhanced assets instead of focusing on course readings, and utilizing a range of insights and multi-tangible encounters to tap the distinctive capability of the learners especially on the said subject which caters enrichment on the skill performances of the learner. Schools can receive various methods of evaluation to discover the qualities and shortcomings of the learners before settling on the fitting educational plan and learning and teaching strategies in the absence of the teacher.

In this trying time, it is hard for the teacher to see the progress of their students especially if the mode of education is only via online platform or on a modular approach. Some students need to socialize, touch, or speak to peers and facilitators to learn. In our present educational system oftentimes, we are now neglecting that fact because of self-paced learning and due to the consequences that pandemic brings.

One of the most important aspects of learning in every setting is motivation that starts and maintains behavior. As a result, when it comes to learning independently in e-learning environments, the level of intrinsic motivation sparks and maintains the interest of open and distance education students. The number of studies addressing the motivation of open and remote education students in e-learning contexts is insufficient, despite the extensive literature regarding the motivation of individuals learning in traditional learning environments (Firat, Mehmet & Kilinc, Hakan & Yuzer, Volkan. (2018).

The primary goal of this study was to determine the level of self-directedness, motivation and student's performance in technology and livelihood education. The school and its organization may encourage teachers to pay more attention to motivating the students for they can directly affect the students' extrinsic motivation and if so, their performances will follow to give a lift.

2. METHOD

This research is primarily a descriptive correlation design, quantitative and correlation study where independent variables are analyzed of possible relationship with the dependent variable. This study is entitled "Self-Directedness, Motivation and Students' Performance in Technology and Livelihood Education".

This study was conducted in Talisay Integrated School which is in District II of Tiaong in the municipality of Tiaong, Quezon among grade 10 students who are enrolled this academic year 2022-2023.

The method that was used in gathering the samples for the study is total enumeration. All individuals in the study population were enumerated either in ascending or descending order. The researcher did not include students which were used in pilot testing and the rest was use in the study. The advantages of this method were that minimal knowledge of the population was required, the internal as well as external validity is high, and it is easy to analyze data.

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There were 152 Grade 10 students of Talisay Integrated School SY 2022-2023 in Barangay Talisay, Tiaong, Quezon, Province as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Distribution of Respondent

Section	Population	Sample
10- NARRA	51	45
10- ALMENDROS	50	43
10- MOLAVE	51	47
TOTAL	152	135

Research Instrument

The researcher used survey questionnaire as research instrument. The researcher developed a questionnaire, which were validated by experts of Talisay Integrated School. The questionnaire consists of two parts, Part 1 was to assess the level of self-directedness of the learners as: dependent learner, interested learner, Involved learner and self-directed learner. Part II of the questionnaire was to assess the learner's level of motivation in TLE as to intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivation. The researcher use modified and adapted questionnaire from Robert J. Vallerand, Luc G. Pelletier, Marc R. Blais, Nathalie M. Brière, Caroline B. Senécal, Évelyne F. Vallières, 1992-1993, on Educational and Psychological Measurement, in vols. 52 and 53.

A summative examination was cross checked by the three education experts, the school head, School CID, and School LR and adapted to DepEd given SLMs. The four criterion categories concentrated on assessing impact, quality, procedure, and substance were used in measuring student's performance Mc Tighe J, (2017). This were the basis in making rubrics to assess students' performance task.

Furthermore, the questionnaire was presented to the panel members for possible revision, recommendation, and suggestion.

Lastly, a letter of approval to use the instrument was presented to the panel members and dean of GSAR to administer the survey to the respondents.

Research Procedure

The researcher followed the following procedures: she requested permission from the school head to conduct the study via a letter outlining the study's purpose and objectives; upon approval, the researcher prepared the study's essential elements. The study followed the following procedures in order to accomplish its objectives.

Conceptualization. The researcher conceptualized the proposed research topic in accordance with the needs of individual students in light of the current educational situation. The proposal for a thesis adviser was submitted to the Dean's Office. Following the office's approval, numerous virtual and face-to-face consultations between the researcher and her adviser and panel experts occurred. The research topic was then flawlessly conceptualized, presented, and defended to the Dean's office. A panel of experts inspected it to ensure that the content is of the highest quality. The panel experts' comments and recommendations were incorporated into the concept's enhancements before the target date of enactment.

Implementation. After obtaining the approval from the school's principal and student-respondents, the researcher proceed to the administration of the survey to conduct the study. First, the researcher creates the survey questionnaire and criterion type rubrics, reproduced, and distributed it to each Grade 10 sections. Students were given one (1) week to 2 to complete the questionnaire as mentioned earlier and the assessment. Finally, the questionnaire and assessment were retrieved for data analysis.

Data Analysis. The researcher collected all instruments and data for analysis. The researcher summarized the data using various statistical tools such as the Microsoft Excel formula. The summarize data were sent to the adviser for cross-checking and the statistician for statistical treatment. After the adviser and the statistician delivered and validated the results, the researcher submitted them to the University's Statistics Center. The researcher waited for the validated results. After it was given back to the researcher, she arranged the charts and tables and evaluated and interpreted them to understand the study's subject further.

Ethical Consideration. The researcher ensured the privacy and confidentiality of the student-respondents' answers and data. The assumed results of the gathered data were between the knowledge of the researcher and the thesis adviser only. The student-respondents' names were likewise not be needed and disclosed in the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data was collected and treated statistically using the following standard statistical tools.

Frequency distribution and percentage were used to determine the profile of the respondents; and the TLE performance of the respondents in written and performance skills.

Mean, and standard deviation was used to determine the pupil respondents' level of self-directedness and Motivation.

Pearson Product moment correlation coefficient (Pearson r) was used to determine the significant relationship between the self-directedness and learner's motivation towards their performances in TLE.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the study's findings together with the pertinent analyses and interpretation of the data statistical processing and the bases for the conclusions and suggestions of the study.

Table 3. Perceived learner's level of self-directedness in TLE in terms of Dependent learner

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
As the respondents I ... learn by our teachers' given lectures and according to what is written on the board what we need to learn.	3.63	.515	Always
can understand our lessons when our teacher coach me what I need to do and give feedback immediately.	3.56	.719	Always
do tasks identified by my teacher one by one	3.57	.641	Always
can finish my tasks with the little push given by my friends	3.44	.789	Often
can finish my activity through guidance given by my teachers and/or peers	3.42	.758	Often
Overall	3.53	.490	Always

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Never); 1.50-2.49 (Sometimes); 2.50-3.49 (Often); 3.50-4.0 (Always).

Table 3 depicts the perceived learner's level of self-directedness in TLE in terms of dependent learner. The study findings with an overall mean of 3.53 and a standard deviation of 0.490, reveal that the learner-respondents are always dependent on their teacher and peers. It simply means that learners are always encouraged to learn with the supervision of the teachers. They become dependent on the teachers' instructions and if the tasks are identified and explained one by one.

Additionally, the highest mean obtained is 3.63, indicating that the learners learn what they need to learn from their teachers' lectures and from what is written on the board. This indicates that they always learn by being dependent on their teacher's instruction while the lecture is visible on the board. It also implies that the learners have a minimal learning span.

On the other hand, statement number 5 has the lowest mean of 3.42, indicates that the learners can accomplish their tasks only through the guidance of their teacher or peers. The result implies that while most learner-respondents often agree with the statement's content, it was the least of their considerations. Nonetheless, the learners who are dependent on their teacher still finish the task, but they do not settle for their own learning.

Table 4. Perceived learner's level of self-directedness in TLE in terms of interested learners

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
As the respondents I ... gain interest to our lessons thru my teacher's guidance	3.64	.566	Always
do my tasks and finish my activity because I want to discover something	3.39	.703	Often
listen to our teacher carefully because I am interested on learning more about it	3.58	.566	Always
feel motivated on finishing my activity even without my teachers' supervision	3.34	.693	Often
can finish my activity because I believe on my abilities and skills	3.36	.592	Often
Overall	3.46	.453	Often

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Never); 1.50-2.49 (Sometimes); 2.50-3.49 (Often); 3.50-4.0 (Always).

Table 4 illustrates the learner-respondents' perception of their level of self-directedness in TLE in terms of interested learners. The research findings indicate that, with an overall mean of 3.46, the learner-respondents often agreed with the statement of the criteria listed in the table. This means that the learner-respondents often perceived themselves as an independent learner. The findings confirm that the learners can gain interest if the teacher provides guidance on their lesson. It implies that the learner's interest can be directly affected by the teacher.

Indicator number 1 achieved the highest mean of 3.64, indicating that an interested learner can always achieve an evaluation from the teacher through her guidance also. This implies that the learners always gain interest in learning by listening to their teacher's guidance to make them feel they want to learn more about it. To add on, it implies that the teachers contribute great impact and play major role on the learner's way of learning.

On the other hand, criterion 4 had the lowest mean, 3.34. It states that the learner can learn without their teachers' supervision.

Table 5. Perceived learner's level of self-directedness in TLE in terms of involved learner

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
As the respondents I ... want to learn new if our teacher let us discover it	3.36	.592	Often
can understand our lesson by myself and can open my thoughts in a group	3.33	.544	Often
am comfortable in participating in our group activity and discussion	3.33	.599	Often

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don't need my teacher's attention and help to finish an activity	3.30	.638	Often
set goals on doing my tasks effectively	3.46	.570	Often
Overall	3.36	.401	Often

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Never); 1.50-2.49 (Sometimes); 2.50-3.49 (Often); 3.50-4.0 (Always).

Table 5 shows the learner-respondents' perception in terms of involved learner. The research findings reveal that the learner-respondents often agree with all the listed criteria in the table, with an overall mean of 3.36 out of 4. It implies that learner-respondents perceived the level of self-directedness in TLE as involved learners primarily when goals were set. The learner-respondents also often desire to learn something new if their teacher allows them to discover it. They can often comprehend the material on their own and open their minds in a group setting. They are often at ease participating in their group activity and conversation, and they do not often require their teacher's attention to complete a task.

Additionally, indicator 5 states that goal setting is often done by the learner-respondents to effectively do their tasks got the highest mean of 3.46. It indicates that most of the time the learner-respondents can be involved in their learning process by meeting up the expected outcome effectively.

Lastly, the indicator that got the lowest mean is statement number 4 with a computed mean of 3.30. It implies that the learner-respondents don't often need their teacher's guidance to finish their task given to them. This means that despite having a hard time completing the tasks independently they often still manage to complete them.

Table 6. Perceived learner's level of self-directedness in TLE in terms of self-directed learner

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
As the respondents I ...			
know how to achieve my study goals, I have my ways	3.43	.641	Often
can learn on my own and just need to consult to my teacher, if necessary, only	3.17	.728	Often
find ways on how I am going to finish an activity without the help of my teacher	3.25	.688	Often
know when to finish my tasks, so I set my own strategy and timeline to do it	3.36	.652	Often
can learn on field or actual set up even without the presence of our teacher	3.42	.604	Often
Overall	3.33	.528	Often

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Never); 1.50-2.49 (Sometimes); 2.50-3.49 (Often); 3.50-4.0 (Always).

Table 6 depicts the perceived learner's level of self-directedness in TLE in terms of self-directed learner. It has an overall computed mean of 3.33. It implies that learner-respondents often know how to reach their academic objectives and have their own methods. They can often learn alone and only need to consult their professors if necessary. They often consider how they will complete an exercise without the assistance of their teacher. They often know when to complete their chores depending on their own plan and timetable.

The highest mean attained during this level is 3.43, indicating that the learner-respondents often know their ways to accomplish a specific task assigned to them by their teacher. It implies that the learner-respondents in this phase often need the assistance of their teacher to finish the task.

In comparison, criterion 2, which indicates that the learner-respondents can learn on their own with a little help from their teacher and if only needed, had the lowest mean of 3.17. The result suggests that most of the learner-respondents often agreed with the statement's content. This implies that majority of the learner-respondents often need the teacher's guidance and presence to accomplish the task given to them.

Table 7. Summary in the Perceived learner's level of self-directedness in TLE

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Dependent Learner	3.53	.490	Always
Interested Learner	3.46	.453	Often
Involved learners	3.36	.401	Often
Self-directed learners	3.33	.528	Often

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Never); 1.50-2.49 (Sometimes); 2.50-3.49 (Often); 3.50-4.0 (Always).

Table 7 shows the perceived level of students' self-directedness. As shown in this table, dependent learners interpreted as always with the highest computed mean of 3.53. Afterwards, interested learner with a mean of 3.46, involved learner with a mean of 3.36, and self-directed learner with a mean of 3.33 interpreted as often. Self-directed learner gathered the lowest means which shows that learners often perceived themselves as self-directed learner.

It indicates that, students perceive themselves as dependent to the teachers' instruction, guidance, and existence. Unfortunately, most of the student-respondents lose their confidence on themselves in doing the tasks and believing that they can accomplish it

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solely by themselves. They often want to discover learning, often feel motivated on finishing their tasks without their teacher's supervision, and often set goals and timeline to finish their assigned tasks.

Table 8 on the next page, summarizes the perceived level of student's learning motivation as to intrinsic motivation. As shown, indicator number 3 had the highest mean of 3.90 which had the same mean as indicator number 5. Additionally, the table indicates that the grand mean of all the indicators is 3.71, suggesting that the learner- respondents' level of motivation as to intrinsic corresponds a lot to the indicators stated and given to them.

Table 8. Perceived level of learner's learning motivation as to intrinsic motivation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In TLE subject I study and participate ...			
1. for the pleasure I experience when I discover new things never seen before specially the different tools or equipment not available in our house	3.76	.859	Corresponds a lot
for the pleasure that I experience in broadening my knowledge about TLE which appeals to me.	3.73	.745	Corresponds a lot
because I experience pleasure and satisfaction while learning new things and actively performing it.	3.90	.827	Corresponds a lot
because my studies allow me to continue to learn about many things that interest me. (e.g., agriculture, fashion accessory, bread, and pastries etc.)	3.64	.918	Corresponds a lot
for the pleasure I experience while surpassing the performance tasks in my studies.	3.90	.871	Corresponds a lot
for the pleasure that I experience while I am surpassing myself in one of my personal accomplishments like finishing the task on our deadlines.	3.46	.960	Corresponds a lot
because I want to show myself that I can succeed in this subject.	3.81	.899	Corresponds moderately
for the satisfaction I feel when I am in the process of accomplishing difficult academic activities.	3.63	.799	Corresponds a lot
because the subject, TLE, allows me to experience a personal satisfaction in my quest for excellence in my studies.	3.72	1.034	Corresponds a lot
because I really like the subject	3.55	.960	Corresponds a lot
because for me, learning TLE is fun.	3.76	.821	Corresponds a lot
for the pleasure that I experience when I am taken by discussions with interesting teacher.	3.66	.821	Corresponds a lot
Overall	3.71	.633	Corresponds a lot

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Does no corresponds at all); 1.50-2.49 (Corresponds a little); 2.50-3.49 (Corresponds moderately); 3.50-4.49 (Corresponds a lot); 4.50-5.0 (Corresponds exactly).

Meanwhile, indicator number 6 got the lowest mean of 3.46. It indicates that few of the learner-respondents want to prove to themselves that they can succeed in the subject for their self- satisfaction.

This finding confirms that learners' perceptions as to intrinsic motivation correspond a lot to their personal goals, the pleasure to discover new things, personal interest, and self- satisfaction.

Table 8. Perceived level of learner's learning motivation as to amotivation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In TLE subject I study and participate ...			
honestly, I don't know; I really feel that I am wasting my time in school	1.92	.783	Corresponds a little
I once had good reasons for going to school; however, now I wonder whether I should continue.	2.37	.853	Corresponds a little
I can't see why I go to school and frankly, I couldn't care less.	2.21	.890	Corresponds a little
I don't know; I can't understand what I am doing in school and in this subject.	1.99	.902	Corresponds a little
Overall	2.12	.538	Corresponds a little

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Does not corresponds at all); 1.50-2.49 (Corresponds a little); 2.50-3.49 (Corresponds moderately); 3.50-4.49 (Corresponds a lot); 4.50-5.0 (Corresponds exactly).

Table 8 shows how learner-respondents perceived the level of their own learning motivation as to amotivation. The study's findings show that all the criteria listed in the table were agreed upon by the learner-respondents, with an overall mean score of 2.12. It simply means that the learner-respondents' perceived level of motivation as to amotivation corresponds a lot. The findings show that the learner-respondents are at a loss for words. They may feel as if they are wasting their time at school. They used to have strong reasons for going to school, but now they are unsure if they should continue. They don't understand why they attend school, and to be honest, they don't care. They have no idea and cannot comprehend what they are doing in school and in this topic.

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Furthermore, the highest mean obtained is 2.37, indicating that there once had good reason for the learner- respondents to go to school thus, as of today they doubt the idea on continuing it.

On the other hand, statement 1 indicates that the learner- respondents feel wasting their time in school achieved the lowest mean of 1.92. While most learner-respondents agreed with the statement's content, it was far from their primary concern. Nonetheless, the idea on the given statements corresponds a little to them.

Table 9. Perceived level of learner's learning motivation as to extrinsic motivation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In TLE subject I study and participate ...	3.84	.836	
because I think that TLE will help me better prepare for the career I have chosen.	3.58	.876	Corresponds a lot
because eventually it will enable me to enter the National Certificate in a specific field that I like.	3.87	.790	Corresponds a lot
to prove to myself that I can complete the tasks given to us.	3.81	.812	Corresponds a lot
because this will help me make a better choice regarding my career orientation.	3.58	.868	Corresponds a lot
because I believe that this subject will improve my competence as TLE.	3.89	.878	Corresponds a lot
because when I succeed in a task, I feel important.	3.41	.995	Corresponds moderately
to show myself that I am an intelligent person.	3.74	.772	Corresponds a lot
to show myself that I am an intelligent person.	3.91	.833	Corresponds a lot
because I need at least basic knowledge to find a high-paying business later.	3.58	.934	Corresponds a lot
to obtain basic information so that I will gain background on the NC II certificate I wanted to enroll.	3.69	1.01	Corresponds a lot
because I want to have "the good life" later.	3.65	.813	Corresponds a lot
to have an additional source of income later on.	3.71	.640	Corresponds a lot
Overall	3.84	.836	Corresponds a lot

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Does no corresponds at all); 1.50-2.49 (Corresponds a little); 2.50-3.49 (Corresponds moderately); 3.50-4.49 (Corresponds a lot); 4.50-5.0 (Corresponds exactly).

Table 9 displays the learner-respondents' perceived level of learning motivation as to extrinsic motivation. According to the research findings, the learner-respondents agreed with all the criteria listed in the table, with an overall mean of 3.84. It implies that the learner-respondents' perceived level of motivation in terms of extrinsic motivation corresponds to them a lot. It simply indicates that the subject, TLE, according to learner-respondents, motivates them to better prepare for the vocation they have chosen. And since it will ultimately allow them to enter the National Certificate in a certain field that they are interested in, they wanted to show themselves that they could perform the duties assigned to them. They feel that this will help them make a better decision about their job path. They feel that this subject will help them enhance their TLE related skills which they feel significant when they complete a task.

As a result, they wanted to demonstrate that they were intelligent. They must have at least a basic understanding to eventually acquire a high-paying job. They gather basic information to receive background on the NC II certificate in which they wish to enroll. They also want to live "the good life" later and have another source of income.

The highest mean obtained during this section is 3.91, showing that the learner-respondent wishes to demonstrate his intelligence. This suggests that this indication on the majority of learner-respondents corresponds a lot to them.

In comparison, criterion 6 had the lowest mean of 3.41, indicating that the learner-respondents feel that they are important upon completing a task.

Table 10. Summary in the Perceived level of student's learning motivation

Learner's Level of Motivation	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Intrinsic Motivation	3.76	.821	Corresponds a lot
Extrinsic Motivation	2.12	.538	Corresponds a little
Amotivation	3.84	.836	Corresponds a lot

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Does no corresponds at all); 1.50-2.49 (Corresponds a little); 2.50-3.49 (Corresponds moderately); 3.50-4.49 (Corresponds a lot); 4.50-5.0 (Corresponds exactly).

Table 10 shows the perceived level of students' learning motivation. As shown in this table, Amotivation interpreted as Corresponds a lot with the highest computed mean of 3.84. Afterwards, Intrinsic motivation with a mean of 3.76 also interpreted as corresponds a lot. Lastly, extrinsic motivation with an interpretation of corresponds a little gather a computed mean of 2.12.

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Table 11. TLE Performance of the students in terms of written skills and practical skills

TLE Performance	Mean	SD	Remarks
Written Skills	34.14	9.977	Satisfactory
Practical Skills	47.35	3.149	Outstanding

Legend: 0-24.49- (Did not meet expectation), 24.50-29-49- (fairly satisfactory), 29.50-34.49- (satisfactory), 34.59-39.49- (Very satisfactory), 39.50-50.00- (Outstanding)

Table 11 depicts the TLE written and practical skills of the learner-respondents. It was written in the table that the written skills with the mean of 34.14 interpreted as satisfactory. It implies that the learner was able to answer the activity satisfactory even though they do not get the perfect score, still they understand the topic.

On the other hand, practical skills with a total computed mean of 47.35 falls in outstanding. Moreover, as it was learning by doing, the students freely express their learning and the teacher-researcher can easily assess her students from giving the instructions, during the execution of the skill and even after the activity.

Lastly, as to compare performance skills or practical skills to written skills, practical skills got higher mean for the reason of learner-respondents like to perform and they show that they excel in it by performing it rather than doing a pencil-paper test.

Table 12. Significant relationship between the level of self- directedness and students' performance in TLE

Self-Directedness related variables	Performance	
	Written	Performance Task
Dependent Learner	-.117	-.026
Interested Learner	-.040	-.073
Involved Learner	-.008	-.041
Self-Directed Learner	-.109	-.091

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 12 indicates the significant relationship between self-directedness and the performance of the learners. Evidence shows that the self-Directedness related variables in terms of Dependent learners, interested learners, involved learner and Self- directedness learners don't have significant relationship to the TLE Performances of the respondents as to Written and Performance task. It means that the performance of the learners is independent of the level or category of self-directedness to which they belong. Other circumstances, on the other hand, may have an impact on their performance.

Table 13. Significant relationship between the level of student's motivation and student's performance in TLE.

Learner's Level of Motivation	Performance	
	Written	Performance Task
Intrinsic Motivation	.289**	.012
Extrinsic Motivation	.303**	.018
Amotivation	.217*	.142

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table number 13 shows the relationship between the level of student's motivation and student's performance in TLE. All indicators of learner's level motivation which are classified as intrinsic, extrinsic, amotivation, has a significant relationship to the written skills performance of the learners. Intrinsic and written are related with computed r-value of .289**.

Extrinsic motivation with r- value of .303**, amotivation with computed r- value of .217** implies that though the variables are related, their relationship is interpreted as weak. Therefore, the result implies that the learners are motivated while there is guidance by the teacher but the guidance of the teacher per item questions is limited. Furthermore, no significant association exists between the learners' level of motivation across three categories and their practical skills. This means that the level of motivation may be provided all at once before the task is completed.

One consideration that possibly affect the results of this study is that the performance of the students in practical skills was based on a group activity. Their activity for that quarter is to build a chicken house and take care of a chicken on it. One grade was given to each group of 10 members. The same happened to the rest of the section. Whereas their written test was given on each of the students which gathers the actual scores of each of the students.

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3. CONCLUSION

The findings gathered in the study led to the formulation of the following conclusions.

The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the level of self-directedness and students' performance in TLE is therefore Sustained.

Findings shows that there is a significant WEAK relationship between learner's level of motivation and written performance. Therefore, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the level of student's motivation and student's performance in TLE is partially sustained.

The hypothesis stating that students motivation did not significantly mediates the self-directedness and student's performance in TLE therefore, sustained. The finding revealed that mediation analysis could not be performed due to the absence of a relationship between the motivation and self-directedness of the learners, causing the total effect to may be non-significant or the assumptions for testing the total effect were not met.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

First and foremost, the researcher expresses her heartfelt gratitude, warm appreciation, and profound thanks to Almighty God, for the guidance, strength, and continuous blessings, as well as the individuals listed below who have willingly and generously contributed ideas, which were used extensively in the preparation, completion, and success this study.

Dr. Mario R. Briones, LSPU President, for his exceptional leadership and dedication to the University for the attainment of the vision, mission and goal of the university;

Dr. Eden C. Callo, Vice President for Academic Affairs, for her encouraging words and her willingness to share her insights and expertise with graduate students;

Joel M. Bawica, MIT Director of the LSPU-SPC Campus, for his unwavering dedication and support to the University;

Dr. Edilberto Z. Andal, Associate Dean of the College of Teacher Education-Graduate Studies and Applied Research, for his constant supervision and provision of necessary information throughout the research process;

Zenaida M. Cuenca, MAT, the researcher's adviser, and a second mother, for always volunteering his valuable time, exerting extra effort, providing unflinching guidance, and providing valuable suggestions, ideas, comments, constructive criticisms, and in-depth analysis of the study;

Dr. Edna O. Briones, the researcher's technical editor, for sharing her expertise and knowledge, for making necessary suggestions, encouraging words, and comments to improve this study;

Dr. Eva F. Puyo, the researcher's statistician, for sharing her brilliant ideas not only in interpreting the data and for her selfless knowledge in providing numerous assistances throughout the process of developing this study;

Mrs. Jocelyn V. Madrideo, the researcher's subject specialist, for extending her assistance by sharing her expertise in the field covered by the researcher's study;

Mrs. Maricar L. Tagara, the researcher's principal at Talisay Integrated School, for allowing her to conduct the research at the school and for her support and encouragement;

Tiaong II District, under the leadership and supervision of Ms. Ma. Lourdes C. Cabanag, DepEd Division of Quezon, and the Schools Division Superintendent, ROMMEL C. BAUTISTA, CESO V, for allowing her to conduct research at Talisay Integrated School and use Grade 10 students' data in her study;

The study's student-respondents and their parents for allowing the research to proceed through their participation;

Mr. Ernesto V. Aguda Jr. and Mrs. Zenaida E. Aguda, her parents, and to her grandmother Marina V. Aguda, for their unwavering love, their unwavering support of the researcher's endeavors, and for simply serving as her motivation and strength;

Krenessa Magda E. Aguda, Ernest Jacob E. Aguda, her siblings, for being the researcher's supporters whenever she needs something or has to do a task relating to the study;

Pvt. King Alfred L. Resurreccion, her boyfriend, for the support, encouragement, and love that he has given to the researcher;

Mrs. Caroline Talastasin, for being a friend, a helping hand and a consultant of the researcher and for making herself available in anytime the researcher need, for being a friend, and for always cheering the researcher up;

Mrs. Lea L. Lopez, the researcher's previous principal at Talisay Integrated School, for inducing her to enroll in her degree, gave word of encouragement to push her through.

Ms. Alixes Palivino, her student-teacher, for assisting her to her class and helping her to focus on her research;

Her friends and colleagues, Mr. John Paulo I. Bukid, Mrs. Cherry Ann M. Nabo, Ms. Gloria O. Palma, Mr. Kervin Lloyd Alexir Gayapa, Mr. Edwin C. Lara, Mrs. Maria Cristina Lara, Ms. Marevelle Brinosa, and Mrs. Nesciel B. Jusi for their encouraging words, lending a hand, and extending their support throughout the research process;

To everyone who has stood by her throughout her graduate studies for their encouragement, words of support, love, and prayers;

Finally, but certainly not least, to ALL AUTHORS whose works were cited in this study and all individuals whose names have not yet been mentioned but have made the most significant direct and indirect contribution to making this research study possible.

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